

SURVEY-A-THON Series

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Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

We are hosting a series of SURVEY-A-THONS to support our OA Diamond and Institutional Publishing landscape survey.

The DIAMAS project's Diamond OA and Institutional Publishing landscape survey has just been launched. It aims to collect information to better understand Institutional Publishing to build capacity across Europe based on evidence and good practice for a more equitable publishing ecosystem.

To support this, DIAMAS is offering a series of SURVEY-A-THONS designed to help respondents complete the survey, addressing issues, questions, or queries which may arise while completing the form. It also allows you to block time in your agenda for the questionnaire before it closes on April 30th. The sessions are offered in a range of languages.

Below are the SURVEY-A-THONS, each sign-up page contains more details about the sessions:

- 30/03/23, 10:00 CET – Spanish (Event closed)
- 04/04/23, 10:30 CET – English (Event closed)
- 04/04/23, 13:00 CET – Croatian (Event closed)
- 06/04/23, 10:00 CET – French (Event closed)
- 07/04/23, 11:00 CET – Serbian (Event closed)
- 12/04/23, 11:00 CET – Dutch – (Event closed)
- 12/04/23, 13:00 CET – Finnish – (Event closed)
- 12/04/23, 14:00 CET – German – (Event closed)
- 13/03/23, 11:00 CET – Polish – (Event closed)
- 14/04/23, 9:00 CET – Nordic languages – (Event closed)

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- 14/04/23, 15:00 CET – Italian – (Event closed)
- 19/04/23, 13:00 CET – English – (Event closed)
- 26/04/23, 10:00 CET – English – (Event closed)
- 26/04/23, 14:00 CET – English – (Event closed)
- 28/04/23, 16:00 CET – English – (Event closed)
- 03/05/23, 11:00 CET – French (Q&A Drop in) – (Event closed)
- 04/05/23, 15:00 CET – French (Q&A Drop in) – (Event closed)
- 05/05/23, 12:00 CET – Croatian – (Event closed)
- 08/05/23, 10:00 CET – Serbian (Q&A Drop in) – (Event closed)

During the SURVEY-A-THON, you will have a short introduction to DIAMAS and the survey's aims. Any issues you encounter while filling in the questions, or queries you might have, will have someone on hand to address them then and there.

You are encouraged to use this session how best suits you – mute your sound and work through the survey, asking questions only if you run into an issue; participate in discussion during the introduction to understand the survey's aims and expected outputs. Finally, there is no requirement to stay to the end if you finish the questions before the end of the session.

We appreciate that the survey takes time and effort; we want to support IPSPs in completing the questionnaire while strengthening the OA Diamond community.

We hope to see you at a SURVEY-A-THON!

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